

Chemical Examination of *Sida Cordifolia*, Linn.

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Sida cordifolia is said to be one of the most valuable drugs in the Ayurvedic system of medicine and has therefore been much used by the Hindu physicians from very early times. It is also used by Mahomedan physicians (Hakims) who consider it to possess aphrodisiac properties.

The air-dried material was secured locally and it was kindly identified by Prof. E. N. Ghosh, M.D., as *Sida cordifolia*, Linn. (Beriá). The whole plant (including leaves, seeds, stems and roots) was used in the present investigation. *S. cordifolia* is said to contain asparagin (Dymock, "Pharmacographia Indica," 1890, Vol. I, p. 207). No other work seems to be on record regarding either a detailed or systematic study of the nature of the chemical constituents present in the plant.

The most interesting finding in our present investigation is the presence of ephedrine in this plant which is widely different in nature from that in which it has been discovered before (*vis.*, *Ephedra vulgaris*), the former belonging to *Angiosperms* and the latter to *Gymnosperms*, two entirely different divisions of the vegetable kingdom.

EXPERIMENTAL.

A preliminary examination to test for alkaloids was made by extracting a few grams of the powdered drug with Perrollius mixture and alkaloid was found to be present.

Several assays were made of the entire plant and the average of 5 analyses by the U. S. P. method (recommended for belladonna assay) showed the presence of 0.085 % of total alkaloids. The highest yield was obtained from samples of plants in flower. The seeds, leaves, stems and roots were also tested separately and it was observed that the seeds contain nearly 4 times more alkaloid than any of the other parts mentioned. The amount of seed varied in different samples and were not sufficient to allow us to use them for the preparation of the alkaloid on a large scale.

For a *systematic examination* of the drug, 200 g. of the coarsely powdered plant were extracted successively with petroleum ether (b. p. 35–50°), ether, absolute alcohol and water. The organic solvent was removed in each case and the residue weighed. Petroleum ether extracted 1.21 %, ether, 0.72 % and absolute alcohol 4.08 % of the weight of the air-dried entire plant. The *petroleum ether extract* was found to contain a small amount of fatty oil and substance similar to phytosterol. They were not examined in detail as having no pharmacological importance. The *ethereal extract* gave no test for alkaloids but it contained a very small amount of an organic acid, probably a resin acid.

The *alcoholic extract* was first freed from alcohol under diminished pressure. The residue was extracted repeatedly with cold, dilute, hydrochloric acid until it was free from alkaloid. The residue consisted mainly of chlorophyll and resinous matter. The aqueous acid-extract was washed thrice with petroleum ether, made alkaline with dilute ammonia and shaken repeatedly with chloroform until all the alkaloid was extracted. The chloroform extract was washed with water, dried over anhydrous sodium sulphate and the solvent removed. The total alkaloids were thus obtained as a brown amorphous mass. Its isolation on a larger scale and further purification is described later on. After removal of the alkaloid the aqueous portion was neutralised, filtered and treated with neutral lead acetate. The filtrate from lead acetate was next treated with a solution of basic lead acetate. The filtrate from basic lead acetate treatment was freed from lead by sulphuretted hydrogen, the excess of sulphuretted hydrogen was removed by carbon dioxide, the solution neutralised and evaporated under diminished pressure. None of the lead precipitates or the final filtrate yielded any crystalline substance and tannins and glucosides were found to be absent.

After exhaustion with absolute alcohol, the drug was extracted several times with cold water. The aqueous extract showed the presence of mucilaginous matter and some potassium nitrate. No glucoside could be obtained.

Isolation and Purification of the Alkaloid.—About 100 kilograms of the air-dried drug were coarsely powdered and extracted repeatedly with rectified spirit until the alkaloid was exhausted. The alcohol was recovered under reduced pressure. The residual extract weighed about 7.76 kilograms. This was repeatedly taken up with

1% hydrochloric acid till the acid extract gave no reaction with alkaloidal reagents. The acid extract was filtered through cotton wool and then shaken with petroleum ether to remove some oily matter. The solution was then made alkaline with ammonia and extracted repeatedly with chloroform. The chloroform extract was washed with water containing a little ammonia, dried over anhydrous sodium sulphate and the chloroform removed. The crude alkaloid thus obtained was dissolved in absolute alcohol and treated with dilute hydrochloric acid until faintly acid. The alcohol was evaporated off and the residue dissolved in hot water. The solution was filtered, cooled and shaken with ether until the ether ceased to extract anything. It was then made alkaline with dilute caustic soda and the liberated alkaloid was extracted repeatedly with ether. The ethereal extracts were washed with water containing a little ammonia, dried over anhydrous sodium sulphate and the ether removed. The residue from ether was dissolved in a small quantity of absolute alcohol and neutralised with alcoholic hydrochloric acid. The alcohol was evaporated off and the residue dried *in vacuo* over sulphuric acid. The dry residue was then treated successively with benzene, petroleum ether, ether and chloroform in order to remove some impurities. Only the chloroform was found to dissolve traces of the alkaloid. The residue was next dissolved in hot absolute alcohol and allowed to crystallise. The crystals which separated out gradually were washed with cold absolute alcohol and recrystallised from dilute alcohol when colourless crystals were obtained. These were then recrystallised from distilled water and dried. The *hydrochloride* was further purified by solution in absolute alcohol and precipitation with ether.

The original aqueous alkaline solution (which was extracted exhaustively with ether) was next repeatedly shaken with chloroform which dissolved out all the residual alkaloids constituting about one-third of the total alkaloids. It has not as yet been possible to crystallise the chloroform-soluble bases. From the pharmacological properties studied they appear, however, to be alkaloids of a similar nature.

The hydrochloride of the alkaloid was freely soluble in water and sparingly in absolute alcohol. It crystallised both from alcohol and water in colourless needles and melted at 215.5° . A mixed melting point determination with pure ephedrine hydrochloride prepared from *Ephedra Vulgaris* showed no depression in m.p. The specific rotation

in aqueous solution $[\alpha]_D^{22}$ was -35.0° (m.p. ephedrine hydrochloride is $215^\circ-216^\circ$ and $[\alpha]_D -32.5^\circ$ to -36.5°). The *aurichloride* crystallised from water in lemon-yellow needles. The *chloroplatinate* crystallised in well-defined orange needles, m.p. 190.5° . Some of the latter was dried to a constant weight in a vacuum desiccator and the platinum estimated. The molecular weight thus obtained with the very small amount of material available was 165 (M. W. of ephedrine, 167).

The following microchemical reactions were also observed :

Reagents.	Reactions.
1. Mercuric chloride ...	... White amorphous precipitate.
2. Millon's reagent ...	... White amorphous precipitate, soluble in excess.
3. Phosphotungstic acid ...	... White amorphous precipitate.
4. Phosphomolybdic acid ...	... Lemon-yellow precipitate.
5. Wagner's reagent ...	... Amorphous precipitate.
6. Mayer's reagent ..	... White precipitate, soluble in excess.
7. Chromic acid ...	... Orange precipitate.
8. Picric acid ...	... Pale yellow precipitate.
9. Kraut's reagent ...	... Orange precipitate, which changed into needles on standing.
10. Oxalic acid ...	... Colourless needles.
11. Potassium permanganate ...	... Amorphous buff-coloured precipitate.

Colour Reactions.—

(1) Concentrated sulphuric acid produced a very pale straw yellow colour.

(2) Biuret reaction: To one c.c. of a 5% solution of the hydrochloride, 1 c.c. of 1% copper sulphate and 1 c.c. of 20% caustic soda were added. An intense violet colour was produced. It was then shaken with 10 c.c. of ether. The ethereal extract which dissolved the colour was evaporated on a watch glass. A gelatinous violet residue was left. This colour reaction is very characteristic of ephedrine and affords strong confirmation of the isolated alkaloid being ephedrine.

Concentrated hydrochloric or nitric acid, or ferric chloride did not show any marked change.

All the above properties and tests prove conclusively that ephedrine is one of the chief constituents of the alkaloids present in Berelá.

Pharmacological Action.—The pharmacological action of the alkaloid hydrochloride was seen on animals and it was found to cause a marked and persistent rise of blood-pressure in anaesthetised or decerebrated animals, but it had no effect on animals whose vasomotor nerve-endings were paralysed by repeated injections of small doses of ergotoxine. The force and frequency of the beat of the heart were increased and the blood vessels were constricted when perfused with solutions of the alkaloid, but these effects were not seen when the animals were treated with ergotoxine. It also caused a well-marked dilatation of the bronchioles and inhibition of the movements of the intestine. These effects resemble those seen with the other sympathomimetic bases, such as adrenaline or ephedrine.

Summary.

1. *Sida cordifolia*, Linn, contains about 0·085% of alkaloids, the seeds being most rich in alkaloids.

2. It was also found to contain fatty oil, phytosterols, resins, resin acids, mucins, potassium nitrate, etc., but no tannin or glucoside.

3. The main portion of the alkaloid was identified to be ephedrine, an alkaloid so far observed only in the different varieties of *Ephedra*, the two plants belonging to entirely different divisions of the vegetable kingdom. The remaining alkaloids, very small in amount, appear to be related to ephedrine as judged by the pharmacological and other properties.

4. The pharmacological action confirms the identification by chemical methods.

In conclusion, we desire to express our thanks to Col. R. N. Chopra and Capt. P. De for the study of the pharmacological action of the alkaloid in detail, and also to Mahamahopadhyaya Kaviraj Gananath Sen, M.A., L.M.S., at whose kind suggestion we took up the drug for our study.

